

Association between Psychosocial Needs, Negative Lust Behaviour with Sexual Risk Behaviours among Young Girls Living in Kigali, Rwanda

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

with SRB impact an adolescent behavior (Nankinga, et al, 2016). Previous report showed that compeer stimulation (CS) associated with PNs induces an adolescent to engage in an illegal substance use that lead to uncontrolled sexual behavior affiliated with robust effect of Unintended Pregnancies (UPs) amongst young girls, Compeer Stimulation (CS), NLB, depression and PN considered as the authentication mark of adolescent's

ABSTRACT

Young girls living in shanty town experience life that may subject them to psychosocial needs (PNs), negative lust behavior (NLB), associated with sexual risk behaviors (SRBs). We aimed to understand how these variables not only independently affect girls who do not purposely use condom or abstain, but also how they shape antisocial behaviors that lead to unintended pregnancy (UP). Participants were 875 girls' members of Young Girls Association (YGA) living in set barracks. We assessed the pitfall symptoms of NLB and SRB (who do not use condom, use condom, abstained) among 19500 sexually active girls as participants. Descriptive statistics and correlation among observed variables for left-behind girls and non left-behind girls were analyzed. The results showed that independent variables were significance to dependent variable, moreover, independent variables were insignificance status to predict SRB. These results provide novel evidence of girls who have had an UP and effectively were ready to change. Our findings provide important information for future researchers based on SRB. Poor relationship, poor mental perceptions, sense of satisfaction are targeted in unplanned pregnancies prevention programs in the key population.

Keywords: SEXUAL RISK BEHAVIOR, PSYCHOSOCIAL NEEDS, NEGATIVE LUST BEHAVIOR

Introduction

With reviews from distinct institutions that are conscious of health, governmental statistics and different authors examined how psychosocial needs (PNs) related

experience of SRB like unexpected pregnancy, HIV positive contamination, incurable diseases (Adedimeji ,et al., 2009). Most of the countries that are dealing with of plenty young girls dropping out, maternal mortality due to unintended pregnancy as it occurs dominantly in the current research (Ntaganira, et al, 2018).

Recent studies showed that CS and PNs may be motivational root to guide young girls to perceive the feeling of satisfaction, uncontrolled emotion, intimacy, which moderate condom use failure and result to UP, incurable disease like HIV. In contrast, CS regarded as constructive model of adolescent to acquire community talent skills, the mirror of bridge to future development pathways (Wing, et al., 2018). Various studies related African sub-Saharan countries found that eight percent of girls had unexpected babies, this prevalence is taking terrific part in large proportions of young girls living in poor social life (Adhikari, et al, 2010).

Prior experience of repeated unprotected sexual behavior can promote risky sexual behavior with implications for pregnancy (Clayton, et al., 2020). For instance, empirical evidence links to female youngster's previous experience of sexual coercion to sexual risk taking reported in different adolescent journal of researchers, due to the perception of confrontation which promote them to uncontrollable life based on peer assistance (Agha, et al, 2004). Existing literature suggests that girls who have a closest friend with sexual experience and physical friendship or partnership intervention are subsequently more likely to engage in sexual intercourse behavior, moreover, he/she may/ may not be protected or use contraception, this can effectively increase the risk for UP (Adeoye, et al., 2017).

The high unplanned pregnancy's prevalence in previous studies coincide with more factors related to personal, family, social problems, the lowest contraceptive prevalence in the world due to numerous factors; like inadequate and unreliable availability of contraceptives, peer group motivation, insufficient health care infrastructure, poor economic issue, poor mental skills, a large number of girls with limited access to health services, lack of productive sexual knowledge, misconceptions and knowledge gaps regarding contraceptive methods (Jean et al , 2014).

An unplanned pregnancy's prevalence under consideration is about 3.2% young girls and HIV positive after sexual activity 0.8% (Michielsen, et al, 2014). The Youth Program on AIDS estimates that prevalence is much higher in secondary schools students (5.3%) than university (1.2%) HIV contamination is (6.3%) (Ingabire et al., 2019). Most of sexually active youth ages 14–26 did a trial of unprotected sex at least 65%, and nearly one-third reported concurrent partners (Iyun et al., 2018). SRB has been observed to cluster in an individual poor knowledge and PNs. Moreover, the majority of youngster living alone in ghetto or with relative families informally known as slums (Thomson, et al, 2015). More studies demonstrated that the youngsters of these areas are growing due to rapid urbanization with the number of female 55% and male 45% (Semasaka, Sengoma et al., 2017).

CS and PNs impacted to create drinking alcohol with the desire behavior among young girls, this is regarded a key predictor to over-thinking and open NLB (Sethi, et al, 2013). Furthermore, there is no more researches of knowledge linked as similar relationship sexual behavior. To understand and address this gap, we aim to comprehend if PNs and NLB moderate the friendship between young girls may incentivize sexual risky. The experience of satisfaction may create an inclination impact of SRB through maladaptive persist to deal with pressure and poor mental health weakens decision-making (Ennifer Hall, et al, 2013).

Present study

This study is carried out to improve the role of compeer friendship perspective in society or partnership associated with unplanned pregnancy's prevention program. Condom use and abstinence were focused key basis to teach young girls of coitophobia based on UP to build up their bright future, we focused on PNs, NLB, to find outcomes from data analyzed in this study and the literature based on SRB as well. Authors examined the role of peer group with the acceptance of positive lust behavior perspectives to victimize negative peer group influence, reinforcement and motivation associated with sexual resulted pregnancy. Besides, we studied compeer perceptive in barracks which young girls look up the mechanism of decision-making, confidence as inner behavior influence. The risk behavior among peers may improve the probability of an inclination toward risk behavior resulting from PNs exhibit in actual risk behaviors (Duits et al., 2020). It was noted that higher levels of sexual engagement among girls with understanding of riskier needs that will give to magnify the risk relationship between PN associated with SRB. Additionally, we aim to attain and maintain specific understanding of the role of various kinds of social needs shape SRB, and assessing the direct effect of observed peer group with numerous behaviors as perspective of engaging in SRB. The result of this study gives implications and strategies for future interventions aiming to reduce UP among young girls living in ghetto and informal urban building.

Method

Study design

We initially invited Nyamirambo women's center (NWC) and Umucyo women's association (UWA) to help us to recruit girls who take part in this study, this study was studied in the field of unplanned pregnancy's prevention trial, the bunch of randomized trial and intervention to prevent SRB outcomes by mobilizing abstinence, condom use, protective sexual behavior. Participants in this trial were member of Young Girls Association (YGA), most of them experienced UP condition and socialized in small-scale enterprise. These YGA are primarily constituted of pregnancy young girls, (1) Already had babies, (2) Without babies, (3) Who tried sexual behaviors once and several times, (4) Never do sex. YGA are made up of entrepreneurial youth who often need social economic support from parents and friends, mental health counselors. Most of young girl's association conference and activities are not formally employed and spend more hours every day at their YGA communion.

Sampling and data collection

We pointed out the barracks for incorporation of active trial in six zones using an adjustment of imputed methodology. To be acceptable for incorporation of active trial, barracks had to have around 19500 members, have been living together at least two years prior to the evaluation, and report no negative behavior within half a year. A total of 32 barracks included the team of 27 members were pointed out, which 875 were recruited, 32 barracks were randomly organized of inclusion in the study. Trough member list completed by team-leaders of these barracks, 875 girl's participants were recognized and evaluated for being accepted. To be accepted as members, they must be registered in barrack, accept to stay there for coming 90 days, be over 14 years older, be perfect to give contact information for themselves and family members or closest friend to facilitate future participant contact to follow-up evaluation for the study.

Accepted participants were asked to self report and give written occurrence, and co-occurring participants filled the baseline evaluation in fall 2013 and the follow-up evaluation year after the launch of intervention. Both questionnaires and interview were directed by trained interviewers in local language using computer assisted Individual interview. A total of 875 girls completed the questionnaires of behavioral evaluation, after each barrack members from one barrack (n=2) were rejected from the study because new information rending them to be unacceptable for participation, resulting in final baseline sample of 19500 girls within 32 barracks. 785 in the 33 barracks completed the follow-up evaluation for 81% retention.

Measures

This study was measured by condom use and abstinence scales associated with status and age, as type of variables operated from girl's self-report condom usage within 12 months (who did sex with their boyfriend/Partner or other people from outside, who used condom during sex intercourse, who stopped doing sex at least 2 years) and as they self-reported were recorded to support data analysis. Girls frequencies reported how many times they did sex with, and how many times they used condom, if she didn't ever do sex.

Figure 1 of change in both condoms use and abstinence

We calculated (Figure 1) girl’s descriptive condom use and abstinence measurement by dividing how many times condoms were used, using that prevalence, members were assigned to one of four types (1) never use condom 2% (2) sometimes use condom 26% (3) always use condom 95% (4) abstinence 37%. According to Li, Turner, Mustanski, and Phillips (2018); (Semasaka, 2017), this type of method is chosen to a continuous variable to reduce the impact of unprotected sex and related NLB outcomes. To evaluate sexual coincidence, participants were asked to report themselves whether they had sex with anyone outside during their partnership in past 12 months.

Figure 2 increasing in condom use behavior during sexual intercourse

These types of variables were measured for both condoms use and abstinence, they were bootstrapped into sampling method (strata with condom use and abstinence) two variables input to be interpreted in increasing simulation and baseline assessment (case weighted both condoms use and abstinence). PNs, CS, closest friend motivation, NLB were studied in self-report questionnaire and assist the variable’s measurement in this study.

Girls were requested to indicate their three closest friends in their barracks by selecting names from the barrack lists.

Analyzing the reported behaviors of all three-best friend for every person, we created an average prevalence condom use and prevalence of friend reporting abstinence and measures members. Concerning to the types of behavior members were asked (1) how many friends do you have that use condom all the times? (2) how many friends do you have were influenced to use condom all the times, (3) how many friends who were motivated to be abstinence? Girls as responded the frequency number as an answers. We created the prevalence friend for which the respondent answered yes for each item. All variables weighted by age and gender included all analyses were measured in the (see table 2), personal corrections between variables interventions were assessed to show changes of all correlation evaluated among observed variables for left-behind and non- left behind girls.

Analysis

Correlations

Table 1 Correlations among Observed Variables for Left-Behind girls and non-Left-Behind girls

Variables	<i>M ± SD</i>	1	2	3	4	5
1. Psychological needs	9.73 ± 2.31	-				
2. Compeer stimulation	9.77 ± 2.64	-0.01	-			
3. Depression	12.14 ± 3.02	0.06	0.13** *	-		
4. Poor mental health	7.19 ± 3.26	0.04	0.09*	0.07	-	
5. Closest friends	7.27 ± 2.98	0.06	0.07*	0.02	0.07	-
6. Substance use	9.73 ± 2.71	0.07*	0.08*	0.23***	0.04	0.05

Note. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

The correlations among observed variables are presented in Table (1) With regard to the correlations PNs was insignificantly correlated with compeer stimulation, depression, poor mental health, closest friend, substance use. Compeer stimulation was significantly correlated with depression, poor mental health, closest friends, substance to predict SRB. Depression associated with compeer stimulation was positively significance to predict sexual risk behavior, moreover, closest friend was insignificantly correlated with substance use, While, substance use was significantly correlated with poor mental health to predict HRTB and scores were shown to the table 2 to explain whether is significant or insignificant to predict dependent variable. Poor mental health was insignificantly correlated with closest friend, and substance use. Closest friend was insignificantly correlated with substance use was insignificant. . Adolescent with depression associated with substance use found to have serious disease like mental disorder, insomnia in conducted research.

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics of Variables

Variables	M	SD	Status(s)	Age(F)
1.Psychological needs	9.73	2.31	-1.22	0.01
2.Compeer stimulation	9.80	2.65	-0.91	1.21
3. Depression	7.19	3.26	-0.74	0.94
4.Poor mental health	12.14	3.02	-0.79	0.02
5. Closest friends	7.27	2.98	-0.61	0.90
6. Substance use	9.73	2.71	0.51	0.53

Note. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

The total number of 875 participants sampled, the M score of psychological needs was 9.73(SD=2.31), the M score of compeer stimulation was 9.80 (SD=2.65), the M score of depression was 7.1(SD=3.26), Poor mental health, M=12.14(SD=3.02), Closest friend M=7.27(SD=2.98), substance use M=9.73(SD=2.71). Psychological needs associated with closest friend were not significant and have no influence with age to predict sexual risk behavior, moreover, psychological needs associated with compeer stimulation was significant to predict sexual risk behavior.

Psychological needs, compeer stimulation, substance use, closest friend, depression, were insignificant with status to predict sexual risk behavior means there is no linkage between compeer stimulation with sexual risk behavior. Psychological needs, compeer stimulation, substance use, closest friend, depression, were insignificant were insignificant with age to predict sexual risk behavior. Adolescent with closest friend associated with substance use, depression didn't predict sexual risk behavior with the age.

Discussions

The association between PNs, NLB and SRB was evaluated from YGA self-report. In fact, the associations differ from student's sexual engagement and sexual influence, they were effectively comparable across sexual self-perception. Furthermore, the current sexual behavior found more risk in relationship with exhibiting analyzed variables of current antisocial engagement. We found non-significant MPH and availability of substance use that associated with condom use and abstinence. The results within this study showed that closest friends are associated with girls sexual influence based on PNs, the mean value of sexual behavior were resulted both condoms use and abstinence after the conducted trial of girls appeared to engage in SRB, CS impacts were associated with condom use in the second assessment that changes to condom use and abstinence behavior interacted with the fear of pregnancy or HIV contamination. In previous research girls optimized their closest friend to confront, moreover, no negative effect outlined (Mwumvaneza, 2017).

Changes in self-report behavior showed that closest friend, NLB and psychosocial basic assets were significant to SRB. We observed multiple significant factors associated with girls' PNs among peer friends who were influenced by their own behavior, imitation, reinforcement in well put social environment and the context of affect behavior among young girls. According to Bandura and McClelland, (1977) psychological sexual lust reinforced in society may increase negative social norms as accepting social interaction including sexual self-concept and orientation with verbal/non-verbal sexting behavior (Marengo, Settanni, & Longobardi, 2019; Nesi, Rothenberg, Hussong, & Jackson, 2017). Additionally, may protectively reduce UPs due to fear of ostracism.

Among girl's CS, we observed that readability of either NLB and peer group experienced and aware of basing public health service were associated with abstinence and condom use. Thus, the girl's perception of ostracism after social verbal abuse and peer group intervention to curb the dignity and social value is associated with both condoms use and abstinence, contrary, negative lust with PMH, alcohol use and unprotected sex during last sex, were associated with UPs. The future researchers should effectively have the potential to reduce unintended pregnancy and related health risk behavior, these preventions strategies should be implemented profoundly sub-Saharan Africa specifically in the place under this research consideration. Additional research is needed to improve the effectiveness of programs and to clarify the most important characteristics of effective programs.

We found no network associated with girl's self-reported behaviors and girl's compeer stimulation in their barracks relationship, girl's behavior changes from self-determination theorized from precontemplation, contemplation, preparation, action to maintenance change behavior. However, the authors showed that self-determination as network to sharpen communication among adolescent (Heather, Patrick, 2018). These results were effectively given previous studies where young girls' sexual behaviors and friendship coincidence including condom use reflect their sexual behavior in the barracks. This may result also girls to have partner outside the barrack associated with sexual behavior in the perception that their friends don't match their friend's actual behavior in barrack by self-decision made to engage in relationship outside the barracks.

Thus, results from the present study are coherent with the publications spotlighting the relationship between PNs and SRB increased to form other behaviors like cheating, drinking alcohol, sexual desire particularly among girls who live in shanty town. Furthermore, the present study spotlights the role of some CS to increase positive social mental factors and the association of internalizing positive relationship. NLB exposed girls to high risk of SRB while they were with their friends in fact that physical motivations impacted the emotional imitations of likelihood. In contrast, positive lust behavior were associated with girls' positive influence based constructive behavior, they empirically strengthened role of abstinence and condom use focused on future life.

We effectively programmed the UPP that focus on a narrow range of behavioral goals and promote a particular social norm (shanty houses) to confide young girl's prosocial motivation. We created and provided skills based

on milt-theory to prevent out cultural and environmental boundaries. This study creates parts of small body literature to examine the influence of compeer related sexual intervention on girl's social development. Recent studies examined the influence of adolescent's sexual behavior analyzed in bisexual HIV positive contamination including men and girl's multi-relational health development (Morrison-Beedy, Carey, Feng, & Tu, 2008).

We found no significant correlations between girl's realization of their friend's behavior and their friends own self-reported behavior. This finding is related to psychosocial needs and observation from peer group behavior. The observation doesn't perfectly match what peers are normally doing as their own realization of own place to react. The recent research has described that youngster pretended to impact consensus or misconception of their peers to risk behavior of owns understanding behavior (Lundsberg, Peglow, Qasba, Yonkers, & Garipey, 2018; Wamser-Nanney & Campbell, 2019). Furthermore, they use the possibility heuristics to explain psychosocial needs from memories of observed behaviors, and the change predictors with our models showing that psychosocial needs were associated with girl's sexual behavior, future research would be better to determine these relationships, a better understanding of these relationships to create change interventions which aim to explain the keys predictors.

Limitations

This study is important and answer how SRB associated with PNs acceptability of confirmation, creating the opportunity for recall bias and have reporting self-report abstinence and condom use. The coincidence of sexual relationship is making a recall bias as a potential large issue in measuring condom use than peer group stimulation of abstinence, given this potential reporting bias all barracks, the coding of sexual behavior variables was designed to minimize this issue of UPs. We represented the influence of mentioned variables and girl's daily lives in the barracks friendship, thus the result showed the importance of barracks in measuring PNs associated with condom use behavior and abstinence to avoid abortion partnered with maternal mortality death and UPs. There was 11% prevalence resulted from the follow-up evaluation, while we accessed the coincidence of poor mental health analytic as social issues that may result the poor mental decision-making to protective capacity on context of sexual SRB and the girls who didn't attended the follow up ended no significant in their risk behavior, thus, the implication of multiple imputation given to minimize the influence of potential bias from reduction pretended from the feedback

Implication for future research

Future studies would deeply try to examine and understand how perceived descriptive PN, CS influence is more closely related to condom use or abstinence, and why perceived behavior would be related to NLB but no poverty influence to shape SRB. A better understanding of these relationships and potential mechanism explaining them would help to explain how to target different types of behaviors that should shape girl's condom use with their peer friend's intervention to reduce UPs by setting more prevention strategies.

Future UP in YGA and related programs should look up the importance based on society and young girl's future in society with as result indicated that the factors act together to shape sexual behavior. The prevention's program aim to promote girl's future health should consider the importance of condom use after failure of abstinence and aim the target understanding of risky behavior to prevent the increasing frequencies of UPs.

Conclusion

In this study, SRB among young girl's living in the area under investigation, we found that PN affects young girl's behavior which shapes sexual risk engagement with external and internal problems associated with NLB in which these multi-variables materialize young girls' poor psychological condition resistance by reaching to UP.

We found that PNs may influence girl's behavior as we found more empirical evidence to prove in self-reported behaviors among girl's who were living in barracks with their closest friend was critically hard to fulfill and conduct this research. We recommend future studies to also promote mental health and civilization by targeting UPs as key important within young girls generally.

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